

The Effect of OCB and Talent Management in Mediating the Relationship of Transformational Leadership Style on Employee Performance

(Study in the Department of Education and Culture of Bireuen Regency)

***Misbahul Jannah, Mahdani Ibrahim, T. Meldi Kesuma**

*Management Department, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study examines the mediating effect of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and talent management on the relationship between employee transformational leadership style. The population was 107 civil servants in the Department of Education and Culture of Bireuen Regency (Depart. Education Bireuen), and the sample was taken as much as the population. The research model was tested using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and Sobel Test. The result proves that Transf. Leadership, OCB, Talent Management, and Employee performance are good, transformational leadership affects OCB, talent management, and employee performance; and Talent management affects employee performance directly and acts as a partial mediation variable in transformational leadership effect on employee performance. However, OCB does not affect employee performance, and does not act as mediator in the model. This finding proves that the employee performance improvement model at the Depart. Education Bireuen is a function of strengthening the Transformation leadership style so that it plays a role in increasing the organizational talent Management.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Talent Management, Employee Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are an important factor in the achievement of an organization's in carrying out its duties. The human resources needed must have appropriate competence to provide optimal performance for the organization and must be able to improve every competency needed by each individual in achieving the expected results (Zefeiti, 2017). Employees are one of the valuable assets owned by an organization, including in government organizations that are called civil servants (ASN). The existence of ASN is essentially the main role of the government in carrying out national development, as well as ASN at the Department of Education and Culture of Bireuen Regency (in this study is mentioned as Depart. Education Bireuen) in developing the education of the children in the Bireuen Regency, Indonesia. Therefore, ASN in each group of positions that have their respective roles is expected to be able to mobilize and expedite government tasks in development, including serving the community. The following is the number of ASN at the Depart. Education Bireuen

Table 1. Number of ASN in Depart. Education Bireuen

NO	Rank and Class	Number of Employees
1	IV-C	1
2	IV-B	2
3	IV-A	2
4	III-D	15
5	III-C	9
6	III-B	15
7	III-A	13
8	II-D	7
9	II-C	3

10	II-B	1
11	II-A	1
12	I-D	1
13	PPPK	37
Total		107

Source: Financial division of Depart. Education Bireuen

From table 1 it can be seen that the PPPK are the employees with the highest number consisting of 37 people. Followed by civil servants groups III-D and III-B totaling 15 people in each. The highest rank group is IV-C which serves as the Head of the Department. To carry out their duties properly, organizations often need to make changes to work methods, policies, and procedures to be able to survive any changes (Seppälä, Lipponen, Bardi, & Pirttilä-Backman, 2011). One of the changes being faced is the COVID-19 pandemic which has caused anxiety and fear for the Indonesian because it is easily transmitted by direct contact with COVID-19 patients. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has brought changes to various fields of life namely education, society, culture, economy, and employment.

In facing the COVID-19 pandemic, every ASN is required to make various efforts to limit activities for the sake of preventing and reducing the risk of COVID-19 spreading, besides that they are also required to carry out their duties properly and give the optimal performance. Activity restrictions are very influential and have an impact on various sectors. Therefore, there is a new life order policy or what is commonly called the New Normal. This is following the regulations regarding the Protection of Workers and Business Continuity in the Context of Prevention and Control of COVID-19 in the Ministerial Circular Letter of Indonesia, Number M/3/HK.04/III/2020 concerning the implementation of the New Normal for the Prevention and Control of COVID-19 in Office and Industrial Workplaces. Therefore, many new policies were made by the Depart. Education Bireuen with the establishment of a WFH (Work from Home) system policy, that all ASN carry out work from home. However, with all the developments of the COVID-19 pandemic in the future, the Depart. Education Bireuen formed another new policy, namely the work shift system policy.

Depart. Education Bireuen continues to review and make adjustments to various work system policies that are implemented according to the direction of the central government, where this has an impact on the performance of all ASN in their environment. Employee performance will be maximized when the organization can manage employees within the organization well. Employees who do not get adequate attention and development from the organization can trigger a decline in employee performance. An initial survey has been carried out on 20 ASN in the Depart. Education Bireuen regarding employee performance during the COVID-19 pandemic. From the data obtained, there were ASN in the Depart. Education Bireuen who have not been optimal in their work so they have not been able to provide the best work results. Whereas with less optimal ASN work will be difficult to achieve organizational goals. Many factors determine the performance of an employee in achieving the best results, namely the leadership style used, talent management applied to the organization, and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of the employees.

According to (Jahangir, Akbar, & Haq, 2004), the leadership role is a factor that influences the achievement of good performance. This leadership role is an element that can influence and actively involve subordinates in achieving these goals through a leadership style. The leadership style is expected to give a harmonious situation to lead to good cooperation in achieving organizational goals. (Ismail, Mohamed, Sulaiman, & Mohamad, 2011) stated that more and more organizations are changing their leadership paradigm to transformational so that an organization can achieve its goals. ASN responses related to the transformational leadership (in this research will often be mentioned as transf. leadership) survey within the Depart. Education Bireuen indicated that it was the lack of motivation from superiors that made it difficult for ASN and hindered them in completing the assigned tasks. Leaders should be able to motivate their subordinates directly to work so that the problems encountered can be resolved quickly and work harder.

OCB has an important role in the effectiveness of organizational performance because with OCB organizations can adapt well to the ever-changing business environment. OCB is a system of cooperation and the willingness of employees to contribute and work in a cooperative system is an absolute requirement in the organization (Hidayah & Harnoto, 2018). This includes not only in-roles but also extra-roles that can benefit an organization called OCB or civic behavior in an organization (Novira & Martono, 2015). An organization that wants its employees to be able to do their jobs or other things that exceed their job descriptions has been proven to have an advantage over other organizations with low levels of OCB (Hui et al., 2019).

OCB can improve organizational performance because this behavior is supported in organizational social relations. Employee contributions to increase company productivity are needed in improving employee performance. On the other hand, with this behavior, social interaction among organizational members becomes smooth, reduces the occurrence of disputes, and will improve performance (Kusumajati, 2014). ASN's response to OCB at the Depart. Education Bireuen indicated that his subordinates were lacking in providing feedback or input related to problems in

the field at hand. This can lead to the wrong direction from the policies determined by the leader. Leaders must also be more involved with subordinates to form good relations so that subordinates are easier to work with and convey their complaints and problems encountered while working and providing services.

(Bethke, Mahler, & Staffelbach, 2011) explained that investment in talent management can produce quality workers with high performance. Responses regarding the survey on talent management at the Depart. Education Bireuen indicated that there is still a need for reconsideration regarding the placement of employees following their talents. Providing a place for ASN who have the appropriate talent, will certainly provide more optimal performance. Studying related to educational background, character, experience, and training for ASN in the appropriate position is believed that it will provide optimal results for the organization in the future.

Based on the background and problems that occur within the Depart. Education Bireuen as previously explained, the researchers were interested in further research regarding the relationship between these variables.

II. Literature

Employee Performance

Performance is a condition that shows the level of achievement of an organization related to its vision and mission (Marlina, Majid, & Madjid, 2018) ; (Moeheriono, 2014). (Mathis & Jackson, 2019) explain that employee performance measures how much each staff contributes to the organization, including the number of output, output quality, output period, workplace attendance, and cooperative attitude. An employee's work over a certain period is compared to various possibilities such as standards, targets, or predetermined criteria. (Riniwati, 2011) and (Edison, Anwar, & Komariyah, 2017) say performance is the result obtained by an organization, whether the organization is profit-oriented or non-profit-oriented, which is produced over some time.

The performance appraisal system in Government Agencies in this case is ASN with periodic assessments of the implementation of the work of an ASN. The purpose of this assessment is to determine the success or failure of an ASN and to find out what strengths and weaknesses are in carrying out their duties. The results of the performance appraisal will be used as consideration in the development of ASN, promotions, appointments in positions, education and training, and awards.

Transformational leadership

Every leader has different behavior in leading his subordinates, and the leader's behavior is called leadership style. Where the leadership style affects the success of a leader in influencing his subordinates. (Runa, 2020) explained that leadership is the process of influencing the activities of an organized group toward setting and achieving goals. Even though the leader should be a figure who becomes a role model for those he leads (Mulyono, 2018). According to (Sumbayak, Anisma, & Hasan, 2017) Leadership is a style that describes the close relationship between subordinates and leader, trust in each other, kinship, respect for subordinates' ideas, and communication between leaders and subordinates.

Fahma (Addin, Kejora, Taufik, & Kosim, 2020) said that transf. leadership can be interpreted as a condition of leaders who provide consideration and intellectual stimulation to individuals and their organizations and have charisma. Transf. leadership is defined as a leader who can inspire his followers to go beyond self-interest for the good of the organization and have an impact on his followers, and the leadership style that a manager used when he wants a group to expand limits and has performed beyond the status quo or achieving an entirely new set of organizational objective (Robbins & Judge, 2017)

Organizational Citizenship Behavioral (OCB)

OCB is employee behavior that is helpful among co-workers outside the Job desk (extra role). (Organ, 1988) stated that OCB is a form of behavior that are individual choices and initiatives, which are not related to the formal reward system but substantially increase the effectiveness of the organization. This means the behavior is not in the job requirements or the employee's job description so if it is not displayed it will not be penalized. According to (Majeed, Ramayah, Mustamil, & Nazri, 2017) OCB is the behavior of doing more than just completing the required work tasks. (Tanujaya, 2015) explained that OCB is an extra role performed by a person in his environment, both within the organizational environment where he works or in the environment where he lives. This extra role is like helping others, not making fights, not complaining, etc. This extra role does not look at what reward a person will receive after performing this action. If this is done in the organization, actions such as helping the work of co-workers will greatly help the organization in achieving its goals because it will accelerate the completion of tasks that have been given previously. (Fajrina, Militina, & Achmad, 2020) explained that OCB is a form of contribution to employees who are deeper than the job desk provided by the organization without obtaining formal rewards. Based on the explanation above, it can

be concluded that OCB is an extra contribution of employees outside of their job desk in helping other employees voluntarily without expecting any rewards so that it has an effective impact on the organization.

Talent Management

Talent management according to (Avriani, Putra, & Amrefri, 2021) is a series of initiatives that the company undertakes through a process identify, developing, and retaining talented employees to align the right employees with the right jobs and at the right time company's strategic goals and priorities of company activities by optimizing the performance of talented employees to create business excellence and achieve vision company. (Harmen, 2018) explained talent management is a process to identify, recruit, develop, and retain employees who are talented to be placed in a place that suits the needs of the company and according to the strategy of the company. Based on some of the opinions of these experts, it can be concluded that talent management is a process of identifying, developing, recruiting, retaining, and deploying talented people with the right skills for the right position in the organization to achieve organizational goals optimally.

Hypothesis and Research Framework

(Moeheriono, 2014) stated that Some of the things that affect performance are transf. leadership, OCB, and management talent. Bass in the research of (Mekka, Lubis, Djalil, & Kesuma, 2020) explained that transf. leadership is the ability of leaders to influence their subordinates, so that their subordinates trust, imitate, and respect them as a leader. (Organ, 1988) stated that OCB is a form of behavior that is an individual choice and initiative, which is not related to the system's formal rewards but substantially increase organizational effectiveness. This means the behavior is not in the job requirements or the employee's job description so that is not displayed. Talent management according to (Avriani et al., 2021), is the process of identifying, developing, recruiting, retaining, and deploying talented people. Talent management has to do with finding people the right person with the right skills for the right position. Can be formulated the hypothesis in this study is as follows:

H1: Transf. leadership, OCB, Talent Management, and Employee Performance are good

The effectiveness of the role of a leader is needed so that the OCB of employees is well demonstrated. Thus they are ready to do more than formal organizational role descriptions expected (Nasra & Heilbrunn, 2015). (Jha, 2014) in his research noted that transf. leadership effect on OCB. Research conducted by (Andrew & Leon-Cazares, 2015) on public sector employees in Guadalajara, Mexico found that employee perceptions of transf. leadership have a positive effect on OCB. Research by (Nurjanah, Pebianti, Handaru, & Foroudi, 2020) showed organizational commitment, transf. leadership, and job satisfaction have a significant and positive effect on OCB for Civil Servants at the Inspectorate General of the Education and Culture Ministry Jakarta. However, different results were found by (Juniartha, Wardana, & Putra, 2016) stated that transf. leadership does not affect OCB in permanent employees of the Industrial Training Center Ministry of Industry of the Republic of Indonesia. Based on this, it can be formulated the hypothesis in this study is as follows:

H2: Transf. leadership affects OCB

Talent management is a process used by organizational leaders to strategically create competitive advantage (Magambo, 2021) ; (Rofaida, 2016). Dimensions of talent management such as attractiveness and retention are very important to influence organizational transf. leadership because directly affect the innovative behavior and performance of the organization (Widodo & Mawarto, 2020). When leaders and organizations highly pay attention to management practices and talents, employees feel more valued, recognized, and appreciated, which will motivate employees to contribute to the organization. Great leaders can manage talent effectively, select the right individual for the position, develop employee talents, empower employees to succeed in their positions, and reward performance (Kim, Lee, & Rhee, 2015). The research of (Putra, Romadhona, Firdausi, Abdullah, & University, 2021) also proved that Transf. leadership affects Talent Management Practices in women leaders in companies based in Indonesia. The study of (Kim et al., 2015) proved the style of transf. leadership is positively and significantly related to the ability of talent management a leader in employees from various industries located in Daegu City and North Kyongsang Province, South Korea. Based on this, it can formulate the hypothesis in this study is as follows:

H3: Transf. leadership affects Management Talent

In the research of (Cisma, 2017), leadership style has a positive influence and greater impact on employee performance where the situation employees feel strength and confidence in doing their job and in making different decisions. Leadership is a process of influence between the leader and subordinates in which a leader tries the behavior

of subordinates to achieve the goals of the organization (Voon, Lo, Sing, & Ayob, 2011). By adopting the right leadership style, leaders can affect job satisfaction, commitment, and employee performance. Transf. leadership can improve organizational performance and image. According to (Walumbwa & Hartnell, 2011), (Atmojo, 2012), transf. leadership, work motivation, and compensation affect employee performance at PT Sago Nauli. Different results were stated (Rafia, Sudiro, & Sunaryo, 2020) who found transf. leadership does not have a direct effect on the performance of the Public Housing Service employees and Central Java Settlement. Based on this, the hypothesis can be formulated in this research as follows:

H4: Transf. leadership affects the performance of Employee

Organizations will always face various challenges such as changes from external and must immediately adapt to the changes that occur in the internal environment organization. In this case, OCB can improve organizational performance because this behavior is supported in organizational social relations. Employee contributions to increasing company productivity are needed in improving employee performance needed. It explains that, with this behavior, the social interaction of member organizations will run smoothly, reduce the occurrence of disputes, and will increase Performance (Kusumajati, 2014). The research (Triani, Halin, & Wadud, 2020) proved that OCB affects the performance of employees of PT Surya Dermato Medica Palembang. (Sari, 2015) also found that there was a positive and significant influence between OCB on the performance of employees of PT. Ultra Jaya Yogyakarta. (Waqiah, Firdaus, & Agustin, 2021) proved OCB affects employee performance and job satisfaction. OCB has no effect on employee performance through job satisfaction of PT Imasco Asiatic employees. (Basu, Pradhan, & Tewari, 2017) stated that OCB can affect employee performance. Based on this, a hypothesis can be formulated in this study as follows:

H5: OCB affects the performance of Employee

Employee talent must be managed by the organization properly with a system of good management. An integrated talent management system in line with other management functions will provide a marked improvement in organizational and employee performance. Talent management has to do with finding people the right person with the right skills for the right position. The bigger companies' awareness of these talents, the more enthusiastic they are to compete to get highly talented employees, either by searching from outside as well as from training and regeneration. Employees who have quality talent encourage companies to continuously improve their company performance to achieve the company vision. The research by (Kaleem, 2019) showed that talent management affects employee performance in sector institutions public in the UAE. Research by (Avriani et al., 2021) also found Talent Management affects employee performance. Employee performance will increase if it can improve Talent Management by improving Recruitment, Retaining, Developing such as conducting training, and providing non-formal education to employees so that the talents possessed by employees can be further increased. (Harmen, 2018) also found talent management affects the performance of employees of PT. Perkebunan Nusantara II Tanjung Morawa. Based on this, it can be formulated the hypothesis in this study is as follows:

H6: Talent Management affects Employee Performance

Concerning the importance of achieving optimal performance, various organizations must be able to stimulate human resources that act as actors and managers so that enthusiastic in carrying out their duties. Leaders can create a conducive work environment and be fair to employees. In such a work environment, employees tend to be trying to do better even beyond the job description of their subordinates, so employees are motivated to imitate the leaders and give the best performance. This has the consequence that every leader is obliged to pay close attention earnestly to foster, mobilize, and gives direction to all potential employees in the environment to realize the volume and workload that is directed at the goal. The high and low levels of OCB and employee performance depend on good whether or not the leadership style and organizational commitment (Vipraprastha & Yuesti, 2018). The research of (Hartono, Hamid, & Yusuf, 2018), also stated that transf. leadership affects employee performance with OCB as an intervention variable. (Mustofa & Muafi, 2021), also stated that transf. leadership affects employee performance with OCB as an intervention variable. However, different results were stated by (Andrew & Leon-Cazares, 2015) found that transf. leadership affects organizational performance better as well as for OCB, but no mediator role of OCB was found between transf. leadership and organizational performance in civil servants in the Metropolitan Area of Guadalajara, Mexico. Based on this, a hypothesis can be formulated in this study as follows:

H7: OCB mediates the Transf. leadership effect on Employee Performance.

In talent management, the leader has many roles in how leaders can manage every human resource optimally for performance maximum (Damanik, 2020). So talent management makes it possible for organizations to make their employees feel comfortable and fit the requirements of their work. This is supported by encouragement from his superiors. Transf. leadership pays attention to the self-development needs of followers and encourages the advancement of talent management for the better. As a result, they play a positive role in the development and progress of the organization. The researchers claim that talent management enables organizations to operate efficiently in their operations. Research by (Putra et al., 2021) found that both transformational and transactional leadership styles were practiced by women leaders in Indonesia-based companies. However, the results showed that there is a partial mediation of talent management in transf. leadership style effect on employee engagement. Whereas full mediation of talent management is supported the transactional leadership style on employee engagement (Sinaga, 2015). The research of (Kim et al., 2015) revealed that the talent management ability of a leader, directly and indirectly, affects organizational effectiveness in both leadership styles. Leadership style transformational is significantly positively related to talent management of a leader on employees from various industries located in Daegu City and North Kyongsang Province, South Korea. But the transactional leadership style does not affect the talent management of a leader. Based on this, the hypothesis in this study can be formulated as follows:

H8: Talent Management mediates the Transf. leadership effect on Employee Performance

The explanation of the concept underlying this research can be described as a conceptual framework in Figure 3 below.

Figure 1 conceptual framework

III. METHOD

Population and Sample

The population was all civil servants (ASN) who work at the Depart. Education Bireuen, totaling 107 people. Technique sampling used was the total sampling/census, where the sample was as much as population.

Data Collection and Analysis

In collecting research data, the author will collect data with the help of a questionnaire. The questionnaire used to collect data is the type of choice that makes it easy to answer and provide feedback because alternative answers are available and do not take long to provide the answer. In the questionnaire, respondents were asked to state their level of the agreement following a Likert scale with an interval of 1-5.

Furthermore, the data collected will be analyzed using the technique of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The hypothesis testing Model (SEM) is a statistical technique that allowed the testing of circuits' relatively "complicated" relationships simultaneously (Ferdinand, 2014). Furthermore, the test of mediation effect will be analyzed using the Baron and approach Kenny (Ghozali, 2018) through the SPSS application and the Sobeltest.

Operational Variable

As for Operational variables, it is necessary to describe the variables research into concepts, dimensions, indicators,

and measures that are directed to obtain other variable values. Variables, definitions, and indicators used in this research are as follows:

1. Transf. leadership (Robbins & Judge, 2017):
 - a) Charisma,
 - b) Inspiration
 - c) Intellectual Stimulation,
 - d) Individual considerations.
2. Employee Performance (Rahman, Iskandarsyah, & Kesuma, 2020):
 - a) Perform work activities perfectly and fulfill the desired goals.
 - b) Complete all work activities.
 - c) Complete work activities on time and maximally
 - d) Optimal use of resources
 - e) Perform work functions without asking for guidance from supervisors
3. OCB (Salim, 2016):
 - a) Happy to train new employees even if it's not their responsibility
 - b) Will give help if at any time a coworker needs work assistance
 - c) Helping coworkers even during break time
 - d) If there is work that has not been completed by a co-worker who can't come to work, will help to do the work
 - e) Often tell good things about the company
 - f) Attending social activities that have been held by the company
 - g) If there is additional work given by superiors, really finish it
 - h) Take the positive side of the problem that occurs
 - i) Minimize and eliminate existing problems
 - j) Have a great curiosity to know developments in the company
 - k) Often provide input to superiors
 - l) Complete tasks based on company procedures
 - m) If there are co-workers who need information, they will try to explain the information
 - n) Always make a list of work plans in advance so that you can finish the job well
 - o) Come to the office before work hours
4. Talent Management (Sariwulan et al., 2021):
 - a) Identification of Employee,
 - b) Provision of Education and Training,
 - c) Work Placement,
 - d) Needed Support,

IV. RESULT

Characteristics

In this study, the characteristics of the respondents were regarding gender, age, last education, as well as rank in ASN in the Depart. Education Bireuen. Based on the data collected, the characteristics of respondents are shown in the following table:

Table 2. Respondent Characteristics

No	Information	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender :		
	Male	68	63.6%
	Female	39	36.4%
2	Age :		
	< 20 Years old	0	0%
	20 - 24 Years old	5	4.7%
	25 - 29 Years old	21	19.6%
	30 - 34 Years old	44	41.1%
3	35 - 39 Years old	31	29.0%
	Education :		
	Senior High School	1	0.9%
	Diploma III	46	43.0%
4	Diploma IV / Bachelor (S-1)	52	48.6%
	Grade:		
	Class VI	5	4.7%
	Class III	52	48.6%
	Class II	12	11.2%
Class I	1	0.9%	
		37	34.6%

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the characteristics of respondents based on gender, it is more dominated by male, as many as 68 people or 63.6% of the total respondents, while the rest are women only 39 people or 36.4%. Furthermore, based on the age of the respondent, the age group 30-34 years is the majority age group of ASN in the Depart. Education Bireuen as many as 44 people or 41.1% of the total sample. Then followed by the age group 35-39 years as many as 31 people (29%). Group of the youngest age ranges from 20-24 years as many as 5 people (4.7%) and the age group of the oldest more than 40 years as many as 6 people (5.6%). Average background of education is Diploma IV / Strata 1 as many as 52 people (48.6%) and Diploma III as many as 46 people (43.0%). Another educational background such as highschool level is as many as 1 person (0.9%) and education at Strata II / Magister level is as many as 8 people (7.5%). The majority of ASN within the Depart. Education Bireuen is ranked third for civil servants with 52 people (48.6%), followed by PPPK as many as 37 people (34.6%). Furthermore, with the highest rank is IV, there are 5 people (4.7%), group II as many as 12 people (11.2%), and the group I only one. Based on data collection in this study, it reveals that the majority of ASN within the Depart. Education Bireuen is a male aged 30 - 34 years old with educational background namely Diploma IV / Strata 1, and has a class rank as a class III civil servant.

Descriptive Research Data

In this study the type of scale used is the Likert scale where the answer is on average there are 5 classes of respondents. According to (Sudjana, 2002), the length of each class interval of 5 classes for all research variables with predetermined categories is 0.8. The following respondents' responses to all research variables can be seen in table 3 following:

Table 3 Descriptive Result

No	Variable	Average Response
1	Employee Performance	4,17
2	OCB	4,10
3	Talent Management	3,95
4	Transf. leadership	3,99

Based on the results of descriptive analysis of each research variable, it shows the results of employee performance responses have an average value of 4.17; OCB with a value of 4.10; talent management variable with a value of 3.95; and leadership variables transformational with a value of 3.99. These values indicate that $y_1 > 3.40$ where it explains the hypothesis Ha1 is accepted, namely **Transf. leadership, OCB, Talent Management, and Employee performance are good.**

Testing the Goodness of Fit Index

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was used to confirm the measurement model with the same indicators (Silva & Alwi, 2008). After the CFA analysis, the structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to test the theoretical model, which is based on goodness-of-fit measures (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2016). The results of model testing are produced by Goodness of Fit indices as in table 4 below after modifications are made to improve the Goodness value of Fit. In table 4 it is known that the Chi-square value is 235.619 and the probability value of 0.058 which is above > 0.05 ; RMSEA value 0.039 is less than 0.08; GFI value of 0.839 which is below 0.90; AGFI value is 0.799 below 0.90; score TLI was 0.974 which was above 0.95; and the CFI value also showed 0.978 which is above 0.95. Even though the values of GFI and AGFI are marginally below the value of critical, according to (F. Hair Jr, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & G. Kuppelwieser, 2014), the GFI and AGFI values are close to the recommended values, so the model is still feasible to continue. According to (Santoso, 2014), overall the model has been fitted with the support of the Probability test results of 0.058, which is above 0.05, which means that the above model is completely fit. Thus, it concludes that the overall model is fit and can be used-acceptable, and is suitable for further analysis.

Table 4. Goodness of Fit

Criteria	Model Result	Critical value	Model Evaluation
Chi-Square χ^2 (CMIN)	235.619	Expected to be smaller than sample	Deficient
Probability (P)	0.058	> 0.05	Good
RMSEA	0.039	< 0.08	Good
GFI	0.839	> 0.90	Deficient
AGFI	0.799	> 0.90	Deficient
TLI	0.974	> 0.95	Good
CFI	0.978	> 0.95	Good

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is carried out using the Critical Ratio (C.R) value at the significant level of 0.05. If the value of Critical Ratio (C.R) > 1.967 and the value of probability (p) < 0.05 then the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) in this study is received. To get this value, data processing is carried out with AMOS as shown in Figure 4 below. The test results can be seen in table 5 following:

Figure 2 Structural Test

Table 5 Hypothesis Testing Results

			Estimate	Stand. Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
OCB (Y1)	<---	Transf. leadership (X)	.772	.694	.210	5.976	***
Talent Management(Y2)	<---	Transf. leadership (X)	.460	.636	.094	4.902	***
Employee Performance (Z)	<---	Transf. leadership (X)	.559	.496	.149	3.747	***
Employee Performance (Z)	<---	OCB (Y1)	.107	.105	.136	.785	.432
Employee Performance (Z)	<---	Talent Management (Y2)	.415	.266	.129	1.980	.048

The table above shows the result that is described below.

1. Transf. leadership on OCB

The test result of thesecond hypothesis showed the transf. leadership variable on the variable of OCB has an effect of 0.694 with a critical ratio (C.R) value of 5.976 > 1.967 at a significant level 0.000 < 0.05. This explains if transf. leadership increases 1 unit, then OCB will increase by 0.694 units (69.4%) and the effect is significant. Thus it explains hypothesis Ha2 is accepted, that is **transf. leadership affects OCB of the Depart. Education Bireuen.**

2. Transf. leadership on Talent Management

The test result of the third hypothesis showed the transf. leadership variable on talent management has an influence of 0.636 with a critical ratio value (C.R) of 4.902 > 1.967 at a significant level of 0.000 < 0.05. This matter explained if transf. leadership increases by 1 unit, then talent management will increase by 0.636 units (63.6%), and the influence significant. Thus it explains the hypothesis Ha3 is accepted, namely, **transf. leadership affects management talents in the ASN of the Depart. Education Bireuen.**

3. Transf. leadership on Employee Performance.

The test result of the fourth hypothesis show that transf. leadership on employee performance has an effect of 0.496 with the critical ratio (C.R) value is 3.747 > 1.967 at a significant level of 0.000 < 0.05. This explained that if transf. leadership increases by 1 unit, then the employee's performance will increase by 0.496 units (49.6%), and that effect is significant. Thus, it explains the hypothesis Ha4 is accepted, namely, **transf. leadership affects the performance of an employee at the ASN in the Depart. Education Bireuen.**

4. OCB on Employee Performance.

The test result of the fifth hypothesis showed that OCB on employee performance has an influence of 0.105 with a value of the critical ratio (C.R) of 0.785 < 1.967 at a significant level of 0.432 > 0.05. This explained that if OCB increases by 1 unit, then employee performance will increase by 0.105 units (10.5%) and the effect is not significant. Thus, it explains the Ho5 hypothesis is accepted, namely, **OCB has no effect on employee performance at the ASN in the Depart. Education Bireuen.**

5. Talent Management on Employee Performance.

The test result of the sixth hypothesis show that talent management towards employee performance has an influence of 0.266 with a critical ratio (C.R) value of 1.980 > 1.967 at a significant level of 0.048 < 0.05. This explained that if talent management increases by 1 unit, then employee performance will increase 0.266 units (26.6%) and the effect is significant. Thus it can be stated hypothesis Ha6 is accepted, namely **talent management affects employee performance at the ASN in the Depart. Education Bireuen.**

Mediation Hypothesis Testing

In this study, there is an intervening variable (mediation), namely OCB and talent management. Mediation test is used to prove the role of mediating variables serves to mediate the relationship between leadership variables transformational on the performance of ASN employees of the Depart. Education Bireuen. Proof of the indirect effect hypothesis between the variables contained in the model will be carried out using the (Baron & Kenny, 1986) and Sobel Test. Furthermore, it explains the influence by comparing the mediating effect before and after the mediating effect of the variable OCB with a Baron and Kenny approach that can be seen below.

Table 6. Regression of the OCB Mediation Effect

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11.396	1.174		9.70	.000
	Employee Performance Transf. leadership	.595	.072	.626	8.230	.000
	(Constant)	9.077	1.458		6.22	.000

1	Employee Performance Transf. leadership	.450	.090	.474	4.989	.000
2	Employee Performance OCB	.075	.029	.244	2.564	.012

Source: Primary Data, 2022 (processed)

Based on the results of the regression analysis in table 6 through the SPSS, identified that in model 1 there is a positive and significant relationship between the variables transf. leadership on employee performance, which is indicated by $\beta_1 = 0.626$, and Sig $0.000 < 0.05$. When the relationship between transf. leadership on employee performance, the mediating variable is included in model 2, namely OCB, which showed a significant relationship ($\beta_2 = 0.474$, Sig. $0.000 < 0.05$). The description above also provides information about the change in the value β of the first transf. leadership, which was previously 0.626 and significant, after entering the mediating variable the value β of transf. leadership to 0.474 and also significant. The OCB mediation has an effect of 0.244 with Sig. of $0.012 < 0.05$ and showed significant results. Based on the above results associated with the method of Baron and Kenny, it reveals that the variable OCB has a role as a partial mediation. This is because the relationship of transf. leadership on employee performance before and after the inclusion of variables mediation was equally significant.

Furthermore, testing the hypothesis of the mediation of OCB variable was also carried out with a procedure developed by (Sobel, 1982) and known as the Sobel test. The following is a test of the mediating effect of the OCB variable that can be described as follows:

Figure 3 Model of OCB Mediation Effect

Based on Figure 3 above is a model formed from the results of the first and second influences on the AMOS program to form a path analysis model (path analysis) with the variable OCB as a mediator. The results of the calculation of the Z value can be seen below:

Figure 4 Calculation of OCB Mediation Effect

From the results of the Sobel test calculation above, the z value is $0.778 < 1.654$ with its $P 0.218 > 0.05$. These results

indicate that there is no indirect influence between transf. leadership on the performance of employees mediated by OCB. Thus can it is stated that hypothesis Ha7 is rejected and hypothesis Ho7 is accepted, namely OCB does not mediate the transf. leadership on the performance of employees at the ASN of the Depart. Education Bireuen.

Furthermore, the influence is explained by comparing before and after the mediation effect with the approach of Baron and Kenny which can be seen in the following table:

Table 7
Regression of Talent Management Mediation Effect

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	11.396	1.174		9.70	.000
	Employee Performance Transf. leadership	.595	.072	.626	8.230	.000
2	(Constant)	8.345	1.421		5.87	.000
	Employee Performance Transf. leadership	.444	.081	.468	5.475	.000
	Employee Performance TalentManagement	.345	.099	.297	3.474	.001

Based on the results of the regression analysis in table 7 through the SPSS identified that when the relationship between transf. leadership and employee performance is included in the mediating variable in model 2, namely talent management showed a significant relationship ($\beta_2 = 0.468$, Sig. $0.000 < 0.05$). The overview above also provided information about changing values β of transf. leadership the first, which was previously 0.626 and significant, after including the variable the mediation of transf. leadership value to 0.468 and also significant. Variable mediation, namely talent management has an influence of 0.297 with Sig. $0.001 < 0.05$ and showed significant results. Based on the above results associated with using the method of Baron and Kenny, it explains that the talent management variable has a role as a partial mediation. This is because the leadership relationship transformational on employee performance before and after the inclusion of variable mediation were equally significant. This supports the hypothesis put forward in this research.

Furthermore, testing the talent management variable mediation hypothesis was also carried out with the Sobel Test procedure. The following is a test of the mediating effect of talent management variable which can be described as follows:

Figure 5 Talent Management Mediation Effect

Based on Figure 5 above is a model formed from the regression result first and second in the AMOS program to form a path analysis model with the talent management variable as the mediator. Value calculation result of Z can be seen below:

Figure 6 Calculation of Talent Management Mediation Effect

From the results of the Sobel test calculation above, the z value is $1.972 > 1.654$ with its $P 0.024 < 0.05$. These results indicated that there is an indirect influence between transf. leadership on the performance of employees mediated by talent management. Thus it explains hypothesis Ha8 is accepted, namely **talent management mediates (partial mediation) the transf. leadership on employee performance in the ASN Service in the Depart. Education Bireuen.**

Discussion

Based on the results of the tests that have been carried out, the following are the results recapitulation of hypothesis testing that has been analyzed by the structural model (SEM) using the AMOS analysis tool as shown in the following table:

Table 8
Hypothesis Verification Conclusion

No	Hypothesis Verification	Estimate	S.E.	CR	P	Result
1	Transf. leadership affects OCB (H2)	,694	,210	5,976	***	Accepted
2	Transf. leadership affects Talent Management (H3)	,636	,094	4,902	***	Accepted
3	Transf. leadership affects Employee Performance (H4)	,496	,149	3,747	***	Accepted
4	OCB affects Employee Performance (H5)	,105	,136	,785	,432	Rejected
5	Talent Management affects Employee Performance (H6)	,266	,129	1,980	,048	Accepted
6	OCB mediates the Transf. leadership on Employee Performance (H7)	--	--	0,778	,218	Rejected
7	Talent Management mediates the Transf. leadership on Employee Performance (H8)	--	--	1,972	,024	Accepted

Source: Primary Data, 2022 (processed)

Table 8, shows the test result of the first hypothesis showed that all variables in this study are transf. leadership, OCB, talent management, and performance employees are considered good by the ASN of the Depart. Education Bireuen. On employee performance appraisal, the statement that has the highest value is "I complete all work activities". This explained that ASN within the Depart. Education Bireuen can complete all workloads given well without experiencing major obstacles. On behavioral assessment OCB, the statement that has the best value is "I often tell good things about my company". ASN must be able to maintain the image and good name of the institution where he works for the sake of convenience in delivering future work programs that involve the wider community. On talent management assessment, the statement that has the best value is "Organization provide education and training to me to develop my talents". ASN received education and training from agencies related to their work. So that ASN can follow the work given. Furthermore, in the transf. leadership assessment, the statement "Superior prevents me from making my own decisions when there is a problem" has the best value. This explained where the chain of command is in the Depart. Education Bireuen is superior hand. ASN must seek approval from superiors regarding issues and policies to be

taken in a job.

The test result of the second hypothesis showed that transf. leadership affects OCB in ASN in the Depart. Education Bireuen. The effectiveness of the role of a leader in an agency is very necessary so that OCB ASN is well formed. Superior behavior that demonstrates transf. leadership paying attention to the self-development needs of followers, guiding their subordinates to see and solve problems from a different perspective, and being able to motivate followers to achieve common goals by working harder will create OCB behavior, where ASN feels cared for and motivated. Intrinsic motivation can lead to the willingness of subordinates to contribute to organizational goals, without expecting immediate personal and tangible rewards. Thus, they are willing to do more than the role description would expect formal organization (Nasra & Heilbrunn, 2015). The results of this study are following the research of (Arimbawa & Sudharma, 2016) proved that transf. leadership, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment have an effect on OCB at PT. Lila Buana Wisata. This result is also supported by the research of (Nurjanah et al., 2020) which showed organizational commitment, transf. leadership, and job satisfaction have a significant and positive effect on OCB for Civil Servants at the Inspectorate General of the Ministry of Education and Culture Jakarta.

The test result of the third hypothesis showed that transf. leadership affects talent management in the ASN of the Depart. Education Bireuen. Organizational leaders have a responsibility to attract, retain, develop talent, and integrate the talents of each ASN into the organizational system to be able to continue to grow. The head of the Depart. Education Bireuen is very concerned about the practice of talent management so that ASN feel more valued and recognized so that they will motivate employees to contribute to the organization. Great leaders can manage talent effectively, selecting the right individuals for positions, developing employee talent, empowering employees to succeed in the position, and appreciating their performance (Kim et al., 2015). The results of this study are following the research (Putra et al., 2021) also proved Transf. leadership affects Talent Management Practices in women leaders in Indonesia-based companies.

The test result of the fourth hypothesis showed that transf. leadership affects employee performance in the ASN Depart. Education Bireuen. As described in research of (Cisma, 2017) leadership style has a greater positive influence on employee performance in which the employee feels the power and self-confidence in doing their jobs and in making different decisions. Leadership is an influence process between leader and subordinates in which the leader tries the behavior of subordinates to achieve organizational goals (Ling, Lo, Sing, & Ayob, 2011). The results of this study follow (Walumbwa & Hartnell, 2011), (Atmojo, 2012), (Pawirosumarto, Sarjana, & Gunawan, 2017), (Mahdinezhad, Yunus, Noor, & Kotamjani, 2017), and (Rita, Payangan, Rante, Tuhumena, & Erari, 2018), who said transf. leadership has a significant and positive effect on performance employee. the research of (Purba & Sudibjo, 2020) also showed that transf. leadership, work motivation, and compensation affect employee performance at PT Sago Nauli.

The test result of the fifth hypothesis showed that OCB has no effect on employee performance on ASN at the Depart. Education Bireuen. Organizations will always face various challenges such as changes from external and must immediately adapt to changes that occur in the internal environment of the organization. In this case, OCB does not affect the contribution of employees to increase the productivity of the company which is needed to improve employee performance. ASN employees are less self-initiated to be willing to help colleagues in need and complete tasks extra seriously. This results are following what was stated by (Fajrina et al., 2020) who proved that there is a positive and not significant relationship between OCB on the performance of PT BPD employees Kaltim Kaltara Samarinda. Research by (Astuti & Oktaria, 2018) as well found a similar thing where there was no significant relationship between OCB and discipline work on the performance of employees of PT X Perdana.

The test result of the sixth hypothesis showed that talent management affects the performance of employees at the ASN of the Depart. Education Bireuen. Employee talent must be managed by the organization well with a good management system. Implemented talent management system integrated and in line with other management functions will provide improvements manifest in organizational performance and employee performance. A successful organization is organizations that create a well-developed talent culture. (Pella & Inayati, 2011) states Talented employee quality encourages companies to continue to improve their company performance to achieve the company's vision. The results of this study are supported by (Avriani et al., 2021) also found Talent Management affects employee performance. Employee performance will increase if it can improve Talent Management by increasing Recruitment, Retaining, Developing such as conducting training, and providing non-formal education to employees so that the talents possessed by these employees can be further increased. Research by (Sumarto & Rumaningsih, 2021) showed Talent Management affects the Performance of Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Kerja (BPJS) Surakarta Main Office.

The test result of the seventh hypothesis showed that OCB does not mediate transf. leadership on employee performance at the ASN of the Depart. Education Bireuen. Transf. leadership can encourage and motivate employees. However, this is not yet created well due to the large number of additional jobs given by superiors, which makes ASN in solving it not serious so that create unfavorable working conditions and low harmonization that can create the behavior of mutual help between individuals is lacking. In addition, ASN is more focused on the implementation or task given (in-

role) but less in-depth on carrying out the extra roles or those that are not stated in the description of the organization's job thus less contributing positively to the effectiveness of the organization and performance. The results of this study are following what was stated by (Andrew & Leon-Cazares, 2015) found that transf. leadership affects organizational performance better as well as for OCB, but no mediator role of OCB was found between transf. leadership and organizational performance in civil servants in Area Metropolitan of Guadalajara, Mexico. Research by (Maharani, Troena, & Noermijati, 2013) also found that OCB did not mediate the transf. leadership on the performance of the employees of PT. Bank Mandiri Syariah in Malang.

The test result of the eighth hypothesis showed that talent management mediates the transf. leadership on employee performance at ASN of the Depart. Education Bireuen. The leader has many roles in management talent, and the leader can manage each human resource optimally for maximum performance (Damanik, 2020). Leaders at the Depart. Education Bireuen can recruit competent and qualified prospective employees and can motivate them. The talent management strategy applied to the Depart. Education Bireuen helps ASN to engage both with their hearts and minds and be loyal to their work with full enthusiasm. Because feelings and emotions encourage individual behavior and are more concerned with the human mind and heart. Transf. leadership of superiors in the Depart. Education Bireuen pays attention to the self-development needs of its followers and encourages the advancement of talent management for the better. As a result, they play a positive role in the development and progress of the organization. The results of this study accordance with the research of (Kim et al., 2015) revealed that the talent management ability of a leader, directly and indirectly, affects organizational effectiveness in both leadership styles. Transf. leadership style is positive and significantly related to the talent management ability of a leader in employees from various industries located in Daegu City and North Kyongsang Province, South Korea.

CONCLUSION

The result shows that Transf. Leadership, OCB, Talent Management, and Employee performance are good, Transf. leadership affects OCB, Transf. leadership affects Management Talent, Transf. leadership affects Employee Performance, OCB has no effect on the performance of Employee, Talent Management affects Employee Performance, OCB does not mediate the influence of Transf. leadership on Employee Performance, and Talent Management mediates the influence of Transf. leadership on Employee Performance. This finding proves that the employee performance improvement model at the Department. Education Bireuen is a function of strengthening the transf. leadership style so that it plays a role in increasing the organizational talent Management. This finding also explains that the model between trans- leadership, Talent Management, and employee performance is proven academically and can be used for further research by adding other variables. Practically, the research results map out several recommendations for research subjects, namely the Department. Education Bireuen.

1. The ASN of the Depart. Education Bireuen can get early schedule a given task so that it can be completed on time and have more time to provide optimal results and better performance.
2. The ASN of the Depart. Education Bireuen can get more serious attention to the additional tasks given to the superior. Because these additional tasks are believed to support the performance results of the main task which is the main job of ASN.
3. The superiors of the Depart. Education Bireuen can carry out position analysis and workload related to a job regularly. This matter needed to assess the talents/skills needed to complete the job well. So that in the future you can position the right person with the right job.
4. The superiors of the Depart. Education Bireuen can provide directions in simple language and ways so that they can be easily understood. In addition, superiors can also be directly involved in supervising the assigned tasks given, so that if a problem occurs, it can be resolved immediately.

References

- [1] Addin, F. N., Kejora, B., Taufik, M., & Kosim, A. (2020). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Kepala Madrasah terhadap Kinerja Guru di Madrasah Aliyah Ghoyatul Jihad Kabupaten Karawang. *Jurnal Idaarah*, IV(2), 153-166. <https://doi.org/10.24252/idaarah.v4i2.16673>
- [2] Andrew, S. A., & Leon-Cazares, F. (2015). Mediating Effects of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Organizational Performance: Empirical Analysis of Public Employees in Guadalajara, Mexico. *Economico Administrativas, Departamento de Metodos Cuantitativos y Maestria En Economia*, 12(2), 71-92.
- [3] Arimbawa, I. P. W., & Sudharma, I. N. (2016). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional, Kepuasan Kerja dan Komitmen Organisasional terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana*, 5(7), 4367-4393.

- [4] Astuti, Y., & Oktaria, I. (2018). Analysis Of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Discipline, & Work Motivation Towards Pt X Perdana Employee Performance. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 10(12), 217-224.
- [5] Atmojo, M. (2012). The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, and Employee Performance. *International Research Journal of Business Studies*, 5(2), 113-128. <https://doi.org/DOI:10.21632/irjbs.5.2.113-128>
- [6] Avriani, E., Putra, R. B., & Amrefri. (2021). Analisis Kinerja Karyawan Ditinjau Dari Manajemen Talenta Dan Manajemen Pengetahuan Dengan Mediasi Komitmen Organisasi Pada PT. Transco Pratama CRF Sungai Betung Dharmasraya. *Jurnal Pundi*, 5(2), 301-312. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.31575/jp.v5i2.370>
- [7] Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173-1182. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0022-3514.51.6.1173>
- [8] Basu, E., Pradhan, R. K., & Tewari, H. R. (2017). Impact of organizational citizenship behavior on job performance in Indian healthcare industries: The mediating role of social capital. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 66(6), 780-796. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-02-2016-0048>
- [9] Bethke, P., Mahler, P., & Staffelbach, B. (2011). Effectiveness of talent management strategies. *European Journal of International Management*, 5(5), 524-539. <https://doi.org/10.1504/EJIM.2011.042177>
- [10] Cisma, F. (2017). Leadership Styles And Employee Performance. *IRE Journals*, 1(5), 6-10.
- [11] Damanik, Y. R. (2020). *Pengaruh Talent Management dan Self Efficacy Melalui Motivasi Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dinas Kependudukan dan Catatan Sipil Kabupaten Simalungun*. Universitas Sumatera Utara.
- [12] Edison, E., Anwar, Y., & Komariyah, I. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia: Strategi Dan Perubahan Dalam Rangka Meningkatkan Kinerja Pegawai Dan Organisasi*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- [13] F. Hair Jr, J., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & G. Kuppelwieser, V. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) An emerging tool in business research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106-121.
- [14] Fajrina, N. N., Militina, T., & Achmad, G. N. (2020). Employee Performance In PT BPD Kaltim Kaltara Samarinda. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 4(1), 55-65.
- [15] Ferdinand, A. (2014). *Structural Equation Modeling dalam Penelitian Manajemen* (5th ed.). Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [16] Ghozali, I. (2018). *Aplikasi analisis multivariate dengan program IBM SPSS 25* (9th ed.). Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [17] Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2016). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)* (2nd ed.). New York: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- [18] Harmen, H. (2018). Pengaruh Talent Management dan Knowledge Management Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Perkebunan Nusantara II (Survei Pada Kantor Direksi Tanjung Morawa). *JKBM (JURNAL KONSEP BISNIS DAN MANAJEMEN)*, 4(2), 114-129. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.31289/jkbm.v4i2.1587>
- [19] Hartono, Hamid, N., & Yusuf, R. M. (2018). The Effect of Situational Leadership on Employee Performance Through the Corporate & Organizational Working Citizenship Behavior as Intervening Variables (Case Study on Office of PT Nindya Karya Branch Makassar). *Hasanuddin Journal of Applied Business and Entrepreneurship*, 1(2), 15-32. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26487/hjabe.v1i2.78>
- [20] Hidayah, S., & Harnoto. (2018). Role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Perception of Justice and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance. *Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen*, 9(2), 170-178. <https://doi.org/10.15294/jdm.v9i2.14191>
- [21] Hui, L., Nazir, S., Wang, Q., Asadullah, M. A., Khaqan, Z., & Amina, S. (2019). Influence of Transformational Leadership on Employees' Innovative Work Behavior in Sustainable Organizations: Test of Mediation and Moderation Processes. *Sustainability*, 11, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11061594>
- [22] Ismail, A. Bin, Mohamed, H. H. A.-B., Sulaiman, A. Z., & Mohamad, M. H. (2011). An Empirical Study of the Relationship between Transformational Leadership, Empowerment and Organizational Commitment. *International Journal of Economics and Business Research*, 2(1), 89-107.
- [23] Jahangir, N., Akbar, M. M., & Haq, M. (2004). Organizational Citizenship Behaviors: Its Nature & Antecedents. *BRAC University Journal*, 1(2), 75-85.
- [24] Jha, S. (2014). Transformational leadership and psychological empowerment: Determinants of organizational citizenship behavior. *South Asian Journal of Global Business Research*, 3(1), 18-35.

- <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/SAJGBR-04-2012-0036>
- [25] Juniarta, I. B. M., Wardana, I. M., & Putra, M. S. (2016). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Melalui Mediasi Kepercayaan Kepada Atasan Dan Kepuasan Kerja (Studi pada Pegawai Tetap Balai Diklat Industri Kementerian Perindustrian Republik Indonesia). *Jurnal Buletin Studi Ekonomi*, 21(2), 181–196. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24843/bse.2016.v21.i02.p07>.
- [26] Kaleem, M. (2019). The Influence of Talent Management on Performance of Employee in Public Sector Institutions of the UAE. *Public Administration Research*, 8(2), 8–23. <https://doi.org/10.5539/par.v8n2p8>
- [27] Kim, C., Lee, J., & Rhee, J. (2015). The Role of Leader's Talent Management Ability in Relations between Leadership Styles and Organizational Effectiveness. *Asian Social Science*, 11(25), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v11n25p1>
- [28] Kusumajati, D. A. (2014). (OCB) Karyawan pada Perusahaan. *Humaniora*, 5(1), 62–70. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21512/humaniora.v5i1.2981>
- [29] Ling, V. M., Lo, M. chiun, Sing, N. K., & Ayob, N. B. (2011). The influence of leadership styles on employees' job satisfaction in public sector organization in Malaysia. *International Journal of Business, Management and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 24–32.
- [30] Magambo, J. K. (2021). Examining the Relationship Amongst Transformational Leadership, Talent Management, & Organizational Effectiveness: A Review of Literature. *American Journal of Leadership and Governance*, 6(1), 37–66. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47672/ajlg.798>
- [31] Maharani, V., Troena, E. A., & Noermijati. (2013). Organizational Citizenship Behavior Role in Mediating the Effect of Transformational Leadership, Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance: Studies in PT Bank Syariah Mandiri Malang East Java. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(17), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v8n17p1>
- [32] Mahdinezhad, M., Yunus, J. @ N., Noor, M. A. M., & Kotamjani, S. S. (2017). The Association of Leadership Styles and Administrators' Performance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(6), 940–952. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v7-i6/3054>
- [33] Majeed, N., Ramayah, T., Mustamil, N., & Nazri, M. (2017). Transformational Leadership and Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Modeling: Emotional Intelligence as a Mediator. *Management & Marketing: Challenges for the Knowledge Society*, 12(4), 571–590. <https://doi.org/10.1515/mmcks-2017-0034>
- [34] Marlina, D., Majid, M. S. A., & Madjid, I. (2018). Mediated Effect of Motivation on the Influences of Emotional Intelligence and Competency on Employees' Performance Mediated Effect of Motivation on the Influences of Emotional Intelligence and Competency on Employees' Performance. (August). <https://doi.org/10.9790/487X-2008062735>
- [35] Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. H. (2019). *Human Resource Management: Personnel Human Resource Management* (Ed. 15). USA: Harvard Business Review.
- [36] Mekka, A., Lubis, A. R., Djalil, M. A., & Kesuma, T. M. (2020). The Effect of Transformational Leadership, Organizational Learning And Compensation Toward Employee Engagement With Trust As Mediating Variable (Study On Employees of Pt Bank Mandiri (Persero), Tbk Lhokseumawe Branch Office, Aceh, Indonesia). *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 3(2), 188–196. <https://doi.org/10.36349/EASJEBM.2020.v03i02.013>
- [37] Moehersono. (2014). *Pengukuran Kinerja Berbasis Kompetensi* (Revision). Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- [38] Mulyono, H. (2018). Kepemimpinan (Leadership) Berbasis Karakter Dalam Peningkatan Kualitas Pengelolaan Perguruan Tinggi. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Sosial Humaniora*, 3(1), 290–297. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.32696/jp2sh.v3i1.93>
- [39] Mustofa, A., & Muafi. (2021). The influence of situational leadership on employee performance mediated by job satisfaction and Islamic organizational citizenship behavior. *International Journal Of Research In Business And Social Science*, 10(1), 95–106. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v10i1.1019>
- [40] Nasra, M. A., & Heilbrunn, S. (2015). Transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior in the Arab educational system in Israel: The impact of trust and job satisfaction. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 44(3), 380–396. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143214549975>
- [41] Novira, L., & Martono, S. (2015). The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Organizational Citizenship Behavior with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. *Management Analysis Journal*, 4(3), 180–189. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.15294/maj.v4i3.8869>
- [42] Nurjanah, S., Pebianti, V., Handaru, A. W., & Foroudi, P. (2020). The influence of transformational leadership, job

- satisfaction, and organizational commitments on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in the inspectorate general of the Ministry of Education and Culture. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1793521>
- [43] Organ, D. W. (1988). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Good Soldier Syndrome*. London: Lexington Books.
- [44] Pawirosumarto, S., Sarjana, P. K., & Gunawan, R. (2017). The effect of work environment, leadership style, and organizational culture towards job satisfaction and its implication towards performance in Parador Hotels and Resorts, Indonesia. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 59(6), 1337–1358. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLMA-10-2016-0085>
- [45] Pella, D. A., & Inayati, A. (2011). *Talent Management: Mengembangkan SDM untuk Mencapai Pertumbuhan dan Kinerja Prima*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka utama.
- [46] Purba, K., & Sudibjo, K. (2020). The Effects Analysis of Transformational Leadership, Work Motivation and Compensation on Employee Performance in PT. Sago Nauli. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 1606–1617. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.33258/birci.v3i3.1091>
- [47] Putra, D., Romadhona, M., Firdausi, N. A., Abdullah, T. M. K., & University, B. (2021). The Influence Of Women Leaders And Their Leadership Style On Employee Engagement Through Talent Management As Mediating Variable. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(3), 3377–3388.
- [48] Rafia, R., Sudiro, A., & Sunaryo. (2020). The Effect Of Transformational Leadership On Employee Performance Mediated By Job Satisfaction And Employee Engagement. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law*, 21(5), 119–125.
- [49] Rahman, H., Iskandarsyah, & Kesuma, T. M. (2020). The Effect of E-Government Utilization of Employee Performance and Its Impact on Work Effectiveness of Kemenkumham Aceh. *International Journal of Scientific and Management Research*, 3(3), 98–105.
- [50] Riniwati, H. (2011). *Mendongkrak motivasi dan kinerja pendekatan pemberdayaan SDM*. Malang: UB Press.
- [51] Rita, M., Payangan, O. R., Rante, Y., Tuhumena, R., & Erari, A. (2018). Moderating effect of organizational citizenship behavior on the effect of organizational commitment, transformational leadership and work motivation on employee performance. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 60(4), 953–964. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLMA-03-2017-0026>
- [52] Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2017). *Essential of Organisational Behaviour* (14th ed.). New Jersey: Pearson.
- [53] Rofaida, R. (2016). Competitive Advantage Through Talent Management. *Proceedings of the 2016 Global Conference on Business, Management and Entrepreneurship*, 615–617. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2991/gcbme-16.2016.115>
- [54] Runa, R. (2020). Determinasi Kepuasan Kerja & Kinerja pegawai, Motivasi, Gaya Kepemimpinan. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen Terapan*, 2(2), 202–222. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.31933/jimt.v2i2.335>
- [55] Salim, D. T. A. (2016). *Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja & Keterlibatan Kerja Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Pada Karyawan PT Graha Mitra Balindo*. Universitas Katolik Soegijapranata.
- [56] Santoso, S. (2014). *Statistik Multivariat: Konsep dan Aplikasi dengan SPSS* (Ed. Revisi). Jakarta: Elex Media Komputindo.
- [57] Sari, L. I. (2015). Pengaruh Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Komitmen Organisasi Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Ultra Jaya Milk Cabang Yogyakarta. *Jurnal Manajemen*, 5(2), 61–69.
- [58] Sariwulan, T., Thamrin, S., Suyatni, M., Agung, I., Widiputera, F., Susanto, A. B., & Capnary, M. C. (2021). Impact of Employee Talent Management. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 10(5), 184–200. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.36941/ajis-2021-0133>
- [59] Seppälä, T., Lipponen, J., Bardi, A., & Pirttilä-Backman, A.-M. (2011). Change-oriented organizational citizenship behaviour: An interactive product of openness to change values, work unit identification, and sense of power. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 85(1), 136–155. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8325.2010.02010.x>
- [60] Silva, R. V. Da, & Alwi, S. F. S. (2008). Online brand attributes and online corporate brand images. *European Journal of Marketing*, 42(9), 1039–1058. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/03090560810891136>
- [61] Sinaga, J. D. (2015). *The influence of leaderships behavior to employee engagement in creating sustainable corporate competitive advantage (case study at PT Perusahaan Gas Negara (Persero) Tbk)*. Universitas Indonesia.
- [62] Sobel, M. E. (1982). Asymptotic Confidence Intervals for Indirect Effects in Structural Equation Models.

- Sociological Methodology*, 13, 290–321. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/270723>
- [63] Sudjana. (2002). *Metode statistika*. Bandung: Tarsito.
- [64] Sumarto, L., & Rumaningsih, M. (2021). The Impact Of Employee Engagement On Talent Management & Knowledge Management On Employee Performance In The Social Security Administration For Employment At The Main Branch Office Surakarta. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 5(1), 268–281.
- [65] Sumbayak, J. S., Anisma, Y., & Hasan, M. A. (2017). Pengaruh Keadilan Organisasi, Sistem Pengendalian Intern, Komitmen Organisasi Dan Gaya Kepemimpinan Terhadap Kecurangan (Fraud) (Studi Empiris Pada Kantor Cabang Utama Perusahaan Leasing Di Kota Pekanbaru). *Jurnal Online Mahasiswa Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Riau*, 4(1), 3168–3182.
- [66] Tanujaya, S. P. (2015). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Dengan Variabel Mediasi Supervisor Trust. *JAB: Jurnal Akuntansi Bisnis*, 14(27), 75–91. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24167/jab.v14i27.962>
- [67] Triani, F., Halin, H., & Wadud, M. (2020). Effect of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Employee Performance at PT Surya Dermato Medica Palembang. *International Journal of Community Service & Engagement*, 1(1), 11–18.
- [68] Vipraprastha, T., & Yuesti, I. N. S. A. (2018). The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Commitment to Employee Performance with Citizenship Organization (OCB) Behavior as Intervening Variables (At PT Sarana Arga Gemeh Amerta in Denpasar City). *International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review*, 9(02), 20503–20518. <https://doi.org/10.15520/ijcrr/2018/9/02/435>
- [69] Voon, M. L., Lo, M. chiun, Sing, N. K., & Ayob, N. (2011). The influence of leadership styles on employees' job satisfaction in public sector organization in Malaysia. *International Journal of Business, Management and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 24–32.
- [70] Walumbwa, F. O., & Hartnell, C. A. (2011). Understanding transformational leadership–employee performance links: The role of relational identification and self-efficacy. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 84(1), 153–172. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1348/096317910X485818>
- [71] Waqiah, Firdaus, M., & Agustin. (2021). Effect Of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) On Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction As An Inetervening Variables. *ABM: International Journal of Administration, Business and Management*, 3(1), 13–27.
- [72] Widodo, & Mawarto. (2020). Investigating the role of innovative behavior in mediating the effect of transformational leadership and talent management on performance. *Management Science Letters*, 10(10), 2175–2182. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2020.3.019>
- [73] Zefeiti, S. Al. (2017). The Influence of Transformational Leadership Behaviours on Organizational Commitment in Omani Governmental Organizations. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 12(4), 111–122. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v12n4p111>